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CREDENTIALING THE LEARNERS MENTAL HEALTH REFERENCE AND PERFORMANCE IN THE NEW NORMAL

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Abstract: This research assessed the effects of covid-19 on teachers and learners' mental health and basic needs in the midst of covid-19. The researchers used the descriptive research method to gather information about the respondents' demographic profile. The data obtained were analyzed using percentage weighted mean, significant difference for the extent of implementation with 0.05 level of significance. Based on the findings, the teachers and learner's response on the extent of the effect of covid-19 on their mental health shows that there is a need to elevate identified services to fully address the teachers and learners concerns in times pandemic. Moreover, data shows that there was a lack of professionals that can guide or help learners in times of emergency situation. Recognizing the significance of these findings, it is critical to offer proper assistance to the school, teachers, and students, since they are the key movers in the real settings in terms of the teaching-learning process and emergency situations.

Keywords: Covid-19, Mental Health, Teachers and Learners, Mental health and basic needs

1. Introduction

Due to the COVID-19 pandemic, schools and colleges all over the U.S. and all over the world transitioned into online classes. The health and safety of everyone is the utmost priority during the pandemic, and online schooling is only the best option during these times (Khalil et al., 2020; Sahu, 2020). At first, it was comfortable and convenient. For parents, no more driving to school, no more preparing of snacks, some kids even attend school in their pajamas. However, in the long run, students, parents, even professors, and teachers have realized the challenges of online classes, especially on one's mental health (Mishra et al., 2020).

Mental health issues are the leading impediment to academic success. Mental illness can affect students' motivation, concentration, and social interactions—crucial factors for students to succeed in higher education (Son et al., 2020). The 2019 Annual Report of the Center for Collegiate Mental Health (CCMH, 2019) reported that anxiety continues to be the most common problem (62.7% of 82,685 respondents) among students who completed the Counseling Center Assessment of Psychological Symptoms, with clinicians also reporting that anxiety continues to be the most common diagnosis of the students that seek services at university counseling centers.

Recent study of active minds student mental health survey (2020) shows that unsurprisingly, mental health has worsened over the course of the pandemic. Almost 75% of respondents reported their mental health has worsened, worsened somewhat, or worsened significantly since the beginning of the pandemic. High percentages of respondents have experienced stress or anxiety (87.03%), disappointment or sadness (78.06%), or felt lonely or isolated (77.47%) during the pandemic. For many respondents, stress (84.25%), anxiety (82.35%), sadness (73.23%), and depression (60.7%) have all increased since the beginning of the pandemic.

Moreover, the COVID-19 pandemic has presented many challenges to students, educators, and parents. Children already coping with mental health conditions have been especially vulnerable to the changes, and now we are learning about the broad impacts on students as a result of schools being closed, physically distancing guidelines and isolation, and other unexpected changes to their lives (Fegert et al., 2020; Imran et al., 2020). For students with mental health needs, such closures mean a lack of access to the resources they usually have through schools. In a survey by the mental health charity Young Minds, which included 2111 participants up to age 25 years with a mental illness history in the UK, 83% said the pandemic had made their conditions worse. 26% said they were unable to access mental health support; peer support groups and face-to-face services have been cancelled, and support by phone or online can be challenging for some young people (Lee, 2020).

School routines are important coping mechanisms for young people with mental health issues (Singh et al., 2020). When schools are closed, they lose an anchor in life and their symptoms could relapse. “Going to school had been a struggle for [some children with depression] prior to the pandemic, but at least they had school routines to stick with”, said Zanon Chiu, a registered clinical psychologist working with children and adolescents in Hong Kong, where schools have been closed since Feb 3. “Now that schools are closed, some lock themselves up inside their rooms for weeks, refusing to take showers, eat, or leave their beds.” For some children with depression, there will be considerable difficulties adjusting back to normal life when school resumes.

Additional issues perceived was there is this newly coined term during the COVID era, called “Zoom Fatigue”. The term Zoom Fatigue refers to feelings of exhaustion after long Zoom classes or video conference calls. It may not be a formal diagnosis, but Zoom fatigue does exist especially in virtual learning. During an online class, there's information overload plus facing the screen for prolonged periods is mentally draining. It's more challenging for students to learn new information, and even though they just sit in front of the computer, they feel like they are physically tired. Virtual learning fatigue is real, and it may lead to anxiety and stress for both students and professors (KYCC, 2021).

Moreover, lack of Interaction and Social Isolation Schools do not only teach new learning from books, it is where friendship starts and fun memories are created. Communication and social skills are best learned with social interactions. Kids, teens, even teachers need to connect with their friends and socialize. But since the COVID

pandemic, there's a lack of interaction and students face social isolation. This greatly impacts a student's mental health. The lack of social interaction in online learning leads to feelings of loneliness, lack of motivation, and isolation. Even adults feel the empty void when they don't get to see their friends, right? Young adults need social interaction in their formative years. Kids need play dates with the kids their age to learn how to socialize. Professors need interaction with their colleagues too. No one wants to feel alone and isolated. This is one of the main reasons why online learning can affect mental health.

In light of growing concerns related to the impact of COVID-19 on the mental health of vulnerable groups, there is an urgent need for research to address mental health burden of the COVID-19 pandemic on students. In the Philippines, recent study of Tee et al. (2020) reported that during the early phase of the pandemic in the Philippines, one-fourth of respondents reported moderate-to-severe anxiety and one-sixth reported moderate-to-severe depression and psychological impact. Moreover, where 200,000 cases of COVID-19 have been reported the highest in Southeast Asia—the project Hope Line, a suicide prevention and crisis helpline, saw a 200% increase in calls in April 2020 (Nortajuddin, 2020).

Furthermore, parent's mental health gets affected too. Online learning does not only affect the students but parents as well. Parents have now become proxy educators, tutors and are getting more involved with schoolwork to ensure them. Even the teachers and faculty get stressed out too. Have you seen viral photos on social media of tenured professors having a hard time teaching their students online? They have years of experience inside the classroom, but teaching using technology devices has not been their best asset. There's also the pressure and worry of teachers losing their jobs because there are some schools that are closing. There's also the additional workload to ensure they deliver quality education to their students. These are all causing anxiety and it's been challenging in the mental health of teachers too.

Research studies on mental health this pandemic is needed. Indeed, we need to act collectively to fight the impact of the COVID-19 pandemic. However, scientific research on mental health problems among students is scarce. Hence this study will be conducted.

2. Purpose of the Study

This research assessed the effects of covid-19 on teachers and learners' mental health and basic needs in the midst of covid-19 at the identified schools in the division of Talisay City Division Cebu during school year 2021-2022. Moreover, it addressed the following effect of covid-19 on learner's mental health: Difficulty in concentration, social relation/social isolation, Changes in living environment, depressive thoughts and suicidal thoughts. It also includes the extent of support services in terms of Basic Services Support Family and Community Support and Specialized services

3. Research Methodology

The descriptive method of research was used in this study, which described data and the characteristics of the population under study. This method answered the questions who, what, where, when, and how. In particular, the present conditions of the respondents as regards to the extent of implementation of mental health and psychosocial services received by the learners and perceived issues and concerns by the teachers. Data was described and analyzed through data gathered using the research

instrument. This research included the INPUT-PROCESS-OUTPUT approach. The INPUT Included the demographic profiles of the respondent groups: age and gender, parents' highest educational, teachers' years of service, relevant training and seminars attended, parents' occupation; and combine monthly income. Extent of mental health issues includes: difficulty in concentration, social relation/social isolation, academic performance, changes in living environment, depressive thoughts, suicidal thoughts and personal needs. The PROCESS considered the administration of questionnaire, data consolidation, presentation, analysis and interpretation using statistical software.

The respondents of the study were the teachers and learners at the identified school in Talisay City Cebu Division. This study focusses in the elementary level and two different sets of research instruments were utilized in this study in order to determine the level extent of mental health issues of the learners in relation to their academic performance in the new normal of education. A transmittal letter will be prepared and address to the office of the district supervisor, requesting permission to conduct the study as the request was approved; the researcher started to distribute questionnaires to the students through their parents. Questionnaires were retrieved and data was collated. Data and information with regards to the study was treated with utmost confidence.

4. Results and Discussions

Table 1. Specialized Services

Difficulty in concentration	Teachers		Learners	
	Mean	VD	Mean	VD
Home as a source of distraction	2.95	MA	3.95	MA
Lack of accountability	2.80	MA	2.97	MA
Distracted by social media, internet, and video games	3.00	MA	2.90	MA
Lack of interactive learning environment	3.10	MA	2.83	MA
Monotony of life	2.90	MA	2.96	MA
Grand Mean	2.95	MA	2.94	MA

Legend: Strongly Agree (SA) - 4.21-5.00, Agree (A): 3.41-4.20, Moderately Agree (MA) - 2.61-3.40, Disagree (D): 1.81-2.60, Strongly Disagree (SD) - 1.00-1.80

Table 1 shows the data in terms of effects of Covid-19 in terms of learners and teachers' difficulty in concentration. Data shows that lack of interactive learning environment got the highest mean for the teacher respondents with a weighted mean of 3.10, which verbally described as moderately agree while lack of accountability got the lowest weighted mean of 2.80 which verbally described as moderately agree. Learners, on the other hand statement refers to home as a source of distraction got the highest weighted mean of 3.05 which verbally described as moderately agree, while the statement refers to lack of interactive learning environment got the lowest weighted mean of 2.83 which also verbally described as moderately agree. This indicates that Covid-19 has an effect on the difficulty of concentration of the respondent groups.

Table 2 shows the data in terms of effects of Covid-19 in terms of learners and teachers' social relation. Data shows that lack of in-person interactions got the highest weighted mean of 3.35 which verbally described as moderately agree, while the statement refers stay up later or waking up later got the lowest weighted mean of 2.90 which verbally described as moderately agree.

Table 2. Specialized Services

Social relation/social isolation	Teachers		Learners	
	Mean	VD	Mean	VD
Stay up later or waking up later	2.90	MA	2.83	MA
Lack of in-person interactions	3.35	MA	2.96	MA
Restricted outdoor activities	3.00	MA	2.79	MA
Irregular sleep pattern	3.05	MA	3.26	MA
Total	3.08	MA	2.96	MA

Learners on the other hand, the statement refers to irregular sleep pattern got the highest weighted mean of 3.26 which verbally described as moderately agree, while the statement refers to restricted outdoor activities got the lowest weighted mean of 2.79 which verbally described as moderately agree. This entails that covid-19 has an effect of the social relation of the respondent groups.

Table 3. Specialized Services

Changes in living environment	Teachers		Learners	
	Mean	VD	Mean	VD
Changes while staying back home	3.15	MA	3.04	MA
Reduced personal interactions	2.75	MA	2.97	MA
Staying longer indoor	3.15	MA	2.98	MA
Increased eating/snacking	2.65	MA	2.99	MA
Inconsistent eating	2.90	MA	2.99	MA
Total	2.92	MA	3.00	MA

Table 3 shows the data in terms of effects of Covid-19 in terms of Changes in living environment on learners and teachers. Data shows that the statement refers to changes while staying back home and staying longer indoor got the highest weighted mean of 3.15 which verbally described as moderately agree, while the statement refers to increased eating/snacking got the lowest weighted mean of 2.65 which verbally described as moderately agree. Learners on the other hand, the statement refers to changes while staying back home got the highest weighted mean of 3.04 while the statement refers to reduced personal interactions got the lowest weighted mean of 2.97 which verbally described as moderately agree. This indicates that covid-19 has an effect on the living environment of the respondent groups.

Table 4. Depressive Thoughts

Depressive thoughts	Teachers		Learners	
	Mean	VD	Mean	VD
Continuously feeling sad without a reason	3.26	MA	4.20	MA
Insecurity or uncertainty	2.75	MA	2.97	MA
hopelessness	3.04	MA	2.80	MA
Linking to depressive thoughts	2.65	MA	3.02	MA
Not eating or eating too much	2.90	MA	2.99	MA
Total	2.92	MA	3.19	MA

Table 4 shows the data in terms of effects of Covid-19 in terms depressive thoughts on learners and teachers. Data shows that in terms of continuously feeling sad without a reason got the highest weighted mean of 3.26 which verbally described as moderately agree, while the statement refers to linking to depressive thoughts got the

lowest weighted mean of 2.65 which verbally described as moderately agree. Learners on the other hand, statement refers to continuously feeling sad without a reason got the highest weighted mean of 4.20 which verbally described as moderately agree while hopelessness got the lowest weighted mean of 2.80 which verbally described as moderately agree. This entails that covid-19 has linked to depressive thoughts of the respondent groups.

Table 5. Specialized Services

Specialized Services	Teachers		Learners	
	Mean	VD	Mean	VD
Counseling services	3.15	MA	3.04	MA
Behavior Management support	2.75	MA	2.97	MA
Orientation and mobility services	3.15	MA	2.98	MA
Speech/language therapy	2.65	MA	2.99	MA
Parent consulting and training	2.90	MA	2.99	MA
Instruments please	2.92	MA	3.00	MA

Table 5 shows the data in terms of specialized support services for the learners. Based on the data gathered, counseling services and orientation and mobility services got the highest weighted mean of 3.15 which verbally described as moderately agree, while speech/language therapy got the lowest weighted mean of 2.65 which was also verbally described as moderately agree. Learners on the other hand, counselling services got the highest weighted mean of 3.04 which verbally described as moderately agree, while orientation and mobility services got the lowest weighted mean of 2.97 which also verbally described as moderately agree. Recent reports by ed.org (2020) noted that separate classroom placements are most prevalent for students with mental retardation (57.0 percent), autism (54.5 percent), and multiple disabilities (44.1 percent), although resource room placements are also commonly used to serve students with mental retardation and multiple disabilities. This indicates that a need for specialized services should be prioritized by the school.

Table 6. Basic Support Services

Basic Support Services	Teachers		Learners	
	Mean	VD	Mean	VD
Water	3.35	MA	3.10	MA
Food	2.95	MA	2.99	MA
Basic health care	3.35	MA	3.03	MA
medicines	3.05	MA	2.89	MA
Safety and security	3.50	A	3.08	MA
Grand Mean	3.24	MA	3.02	MA

Table 6 shows the data in terms of basic support services for the learners. Based on the data gathered, safety and security got the highest weighted mean of 3.50 which verbally described as agree, while food got the lowest weighted mean of 2.95 which was also verbally described as moderately agree. This indicates that schools promote safety and security inside however in terms of food, teacher respondents perceived it as moderately given to the learners. Meanwhile, learners on the other hand, water got the highest weighted mean of 3.10 which verbally described as moderately agree,

while medicines got the lowest weighted mean of 2.89 which also verbally described as moderately agree. This indicates that water was perceived by the learners as abundant in the schools while medicines were scarce or not available. According to Butler et al. (2020) there are a significant number of students on maintenance medications for chronic diseases or with diagnoses that may result in medical emergencies requiring administration of medications in school.

Moreover, previous article published by Steroplast Healthcare (2014) when bacteria and viruses enter a school, they can spread like wildfire. Children are far less focused on washing their hands throughout the day. Break time activities will see them in very close contact with each other. In turn, every school needs to have the right tools to help mitigate the spread of germs through the grounds. From spill kits and disinfectant to latex gloves and aprons. There will be a variety of infection control products that could save both teachers and students from pesky illnesses and lengthy periods of convalescence. The likes of non-contact thermometers and sanitizing alcohol gel will also help a great deal. As will ensuring that signs are displayed across the school reminding students to wash their hands. This entails that availability of medicine at school is very important for emergency purposes.

Table 7. Community and Family Support

Community and Family Support	Teachers		Learners	
	Mean	VD	Mean	VD
Family and Tracing and Reunification	2.95	MA	2.97	MA
Livelihood activities	2.80	MA	2.83	MA
Activation of social networks	3.00	MA	2.90	MA
Supportive parenting programs	3.10	MA	3.05	MA
Formal and non-formal educational activities	2.90	MA	2.96	MA
Grand Mean	2.95	MA	2.94	MA

Table 7 shows the data in terms of community and family support services for the learners. Based on the data gathered, supportive parenting programs got the highest weighted mean of 3.10 which verbally described as moderately agree, while livelihood activities got the lowest weighted mean of 2.80 which was also verbally described as moderately agree. This indicates that schools provide supporting parenting programs that help parents understand the needs of their children. Learners on the other hand, supporting parenting program got the highest weighted mean of 3.05 which verbally described as moderately agree, while livelihood activities got the lowest weighted mean of 2.83 which also verbally described as moderately agree. This indicates that livelihood activities were not prioritize by the school. Recent study of Shimizu et al. (2016) noted that livelihood program appeared to be scaled up and modified to better improve participants' mental health. In addition, IFRC (2019) emphasized that a livelihood is a means of making a living. It encompasses people's capabilities, assets, income and activities required to secure the necessities of life. This implied that livelihood activities help learners overcome mental health and psychological concerns.

Table 8. Test of Significant Difference

Source of Difference	Mean	n	z	Zcrit	p-value
Teacher	2.97	20	3.1421	1.96	0.0016***

Learner	3.02	150			
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Table 8 shows the significant difference of the perception of the respondents on the effect of covid-19 on the mental health of the learners and teachers. Data shows that data is significant at 0.05, this indicates that the null hypothesis was rejected. Thus, there is significant difference.

5. Conclusion

This research assessed the mental health and psychosocial services in times of covid-19 at the identified schools in Talisay City Cebu Division. Based on the findings, the teachers and learner's response on the extent of the effect of covid-19 on their mental health shows that there is a need to elevate identified services to fully address the teachers and learners concerns in times pandemic. Moreover, data shows that there was a lack of professionals that can guide or help learners in times of emergency situation. Recognizing the significance of these findings, it is critical to offer proper assistance to the school, teachers, and students, since they are the key movers in the real settings in terms of the teaching-learning process and emergency situations.

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